

On Some Characterization of *GS*-exponential kind of Convex Functions

Ehtesham Akhter^a and Musavvir Ali^{b,*}

^{a, b} Department of Mathematics,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202002, India

Abstract

This manuscript introduces the idea of *GS*-exponential kind of convex functions and some of their algebraic features, and we introduce a new class *GS*-exponential kind of convex sets. In addition, we describe certain fundamental *GS*-exponential kind of convex function with characteristics in both the general and the differentiable cases. We establish the sufficient conditions of optimality and offer the proof for unconstrained as well as inequality-constrained programming while considering the assumption of *GS*-exponential kind of convexity.

MSC: 26A51, 26B25, 90C26.

Keywords: *GS*-exponential kind of convex functions and sets, Inequalities, Optimality conditions, Optimization.

1 Introduction

Due to the importance of convexity and its generalisations in the study of optimality to resolve mathematical issues, researchers have concentrated a lot of their efforts on generalised convex functions for this purpose. As an illustration, Hudzik and Maligranda (1994) [7], investigated at two distinct forms of *s*-convexity and found that *s*-convexity in the next meaning is basically more significant than in the first sense whenever ($0 < s < 1$). Youness (1999) [20] expanded the definitions of convex sets and functions to create a new class of sets and functions known as *E*-convex sets and *E*-convex functions. Yang (2001) [19] enhanced Youness's paper [20] by incorporating certain illustrations.

In recent years, academic experts have given these generalized convex functions in additional consideration. The semi-preinvex functions were studied by X.J. Long and J.W. Peng in 2006 [12] as a generalization of the semi-preinvex functions and

the b -vex functions. Y. Syau et al. (2009) [17] developed the E - b -vex function family, a novel class of functions which are the generalizations of b -vex functions and E -vex functions. In 2011, T. Emam investigated a novel class of functions known as approximately b -invex functions. He also discussed some of its properties and discovered the necessary optimality conditions for nonlinear programming using these functions. In their investigation of a novel class of generalized sub- b -convex functions and sub- b -convex sets, M.T. Chao et al. (2012) [13] showed the conditions for the existence of optimal solutions for both unconstrained and inequality-constrained sub- b -convex programming.

The study in our paper aims to introduce a new class of generalized exponential kind of convex functions termed as GS -exponential kind of convex functions and explores certain characteristics of the same class. This paper draws inspiration from a number of research papers [2, 5, 6, 8, 10, 14–16, 18, 21]. Additionally, we offer the adequate GS -exponential kind of convexity-derived criteria of optimality for programming with variables which are both unconstrained and inequality-constrained.

2 Preliminaries

We will go through the definitions of sub- b - s -convexity, exponential kind of convexity, and s -convexity of functions in this section of the manuscript. For the remainder of this work, let V stand for any non-empty convex subset in \mathbb{R}^n .

Definition 2.1. [11] The function $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is known as sub- b - s -convex in the second sense associated with the map $G : V \times V \times (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, if

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq a^s Q(m_1) + (1 - a)^s Q(m_2) + G(m_1, m_2, s)$$

holds for all $m_1, m_2 \in V, a \in [0, 1]$ and for any fixed $s \in (0, 1]$.

Definition 2.2. [7] The function $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is known as s -convex in the second sense, if for all $m_1, m_2 \in V, a \in [0, 1]$ and for any fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, we have

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq a^s Q(m_1) + (1 - a)^s Q(m_2)$$

Definition 2.3. [9] A positive function $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is known as exponential kind of convex function, if

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq (e^a - 1)Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)Q(m_2)$$

holds for all $m_1, m_2 \in V, a \in [0, 1]$.

The concepts defined as in 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3, motivates us to explore a new idea known as GS -exponential kind of convex function.

3 Main Results

Definition 3.1. The function $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is known as GS-exponential kind of convex function on V associated with the map $G : V \times V \times (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, if

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \quad (3.1)$$

holds for each $m_1, m_2 \in V, a \in [0, 1]$ and for any fixed $s \in (0, 1]$.

Remark 3.1. If we take $s = 1$, $Q(m_1)$ is non-negative and $G(m_1, m_2, s) = 0$, the GS-exponential kind of convex function reduces to be exponential kind of convex function.

Example 3.2. Let $Q : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be defined as

$$Q(m) = m^2 + e^m + c, \quad c > 0$$

and also let $G : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be defined as $G(m, n, s) = m^2 + n^2 + s^2$. Then, it can be easily seen that Q is a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G .

Theorem 3.3. If $Q_1, Q_2 : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G_1, G_2 respectively, then $Q_1 + Q_2$ and βQ_1 , ($\beta \geq 0$) are also a GS-exponential kind of convex function.

Corollary 3.3.1. If $Q_i : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map $G_i : V \times V \times (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$), respectively, then $Q = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i Q_i$, $\beta \geq 0$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map $G = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i G_i$.

Lemma 3.4. For all $a \in [0, 1]$ and $s \in (0, 1]$, the inequalities $(e^a - 1)^s \geq a$ and $(e^{1-a} - 1)^s \geq 1 - a$ hold.

Proof. The proof of Theorem 3.3, Lemma 3.4 and Corollary 3.3.1 are quite trivial. □

Proposition 3.5. Every convex function is GS-exponential kind of convex function if it has a map G associated with it that is non-negative.

Proof. By Lemma 3.4, we have $(e^a - 1)^s \geq a$ and $(e^{1-a} - 1)^s \geq 1 - a$, for all $a \in [0, 1]$ and $s \in (0, 1]$. As Q is convex, then by convexity, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) &\leq aQ(m_1) + (1 - a)Q(m_2) \\ &\leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.6. *If $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G and $S : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a non-negative function in addition to being linear, then $S \circ Q$ is a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map $S \circ G$.*

Proof. As Q is a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G and S is a non-negative as well as a linear function, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} S \circ Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) &= S(Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2)) \\ &\leq S((e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) \\ &\quad + aG(m_1, m_2, s)) \\ &= (e^a - 1)^s S(Q(m_1)) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s S(Q(m_2)) \\ &\quad + aS(G(m_1, m_2, s)) \\ &= (e^a - 1)^s (S \circ Q)(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s (S \circ Q)(m_2) \\ &\quad + a(S \circ G)(m_1, m_2, s). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $S \circ Q$ is the convex function of the GS-exponential kind associated with the map $S \circ G$. \square

Definition 3.7. Assume that U be a non-empty subset of \mathbb{R}^{n+1} . Then, U is known as GS-exponential kind of convex set associated with the map $G : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ if for all $(m_1, \alpha_1), (m_2, \alpha_2) \in U, m_1, m_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n, a \in [0, 1]$ and some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, we have

$$(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2, (e^a - 1)^s \alpha_1 + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s \alpha_2 + aG(m_1, m_2, s)) \in U.$$

Now, we provide a characterization of GS-exponential kind of convex function $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ based on their respective epigraphs, given by

$$E(Q) = \{(m, \alpha) : m \in V, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}, Q(m) \leq \alpha\}.$$

Theorem 3.8. *A function $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map $G : V \times V \times (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, if and only if $E(Q)$ is a GS-exponential kind of convex set associated with the map G .*

Proof. Let Q be a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G . Assume that $(m_1, \alpha_1), (m_2, \alpha_2) \in E(Q)$. This implies that $Q(m_1) \leq \alpha_1$ and $Q(m_2) \leq \alpha_2$. Then, for all $m_1, m_2 \in V, a \in [0, 1]$ and some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) &\leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &\leq (e^a - 1)^s \alpha_1 + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s \alpha_2 + aG(m_1, m_2, s). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by definition of epigraph, we obtain

$$(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2, (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s)) \in E(Q).$$

Hence, $E(Q)$ is a GS-exponential kind of convex set associated with the map G .

Conversely, suppose that $E(Q)$ is a GS-exponential kind of convex set associated with the map G . Take $m_1, m_2 \in V$, then $(m_1, Q(m_1)), (m_2, Q(m_2)) \in E(Q)$. So, for $a \in [0, 1]$ and for any fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, we get

$$(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2, (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s)) \in E(Q).$$

\Rightarrow

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s).$$

Therefore, Q is a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G . \square

Theorem 3.9. Assume that $m_2 > 0$ and $Q_\beta : [m_1, m_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a family of numerical functions associated with the map G_β and each G_β is a GS-exponential kind of convex functions and each G_β is bounded function, also assume that $Q(m) = \sup_\beta Q_\beta(m)$ and $G(m_1, m_2, s) = \sup_\beta G_\beta(m_1, m_2, s)$. If the set (non-empty) $K = \{r \in [m_1, m_2] \mid Q(r) < \infty\}$, then K is an interval and Q is GS-exponential kind of convex function on K .

Proof. Take any $m_1, m_2 \in K$ and $a \in [0, 1]$. And as Q is a GS-exponential kind of convex function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) &= \sup_\beta Q_\beta(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \\ &\leq \sup_\beta [(e^a - 1)^s Q_\beta(m_1) \\ &\quad + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q_\beta(m_2) + aG_\beta(m_1, m_2, s)] \\ &\leq (e^a - 1)^s \sup_\beta Q_\beta(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s \sup_\beta Q_\beta(m_2) \\ &\quad + a \sup_\beta G_\beta(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &= (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &< \infty. \end{aligned}$$

\square

Theorem 3.10. Let $Q : [m_1, m_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map $G : [m_1, m_2] \times [m_1, m_2] \times (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and also let $G(m_1, m_2, s)$ is bounded, then Q is also bounded on $[m_1, m_2]$.

Proof. Assume that $F = \max\{Q(m_1), Q(m_2)\}$, $E = \max G(m_1, m_2, s) < \infty$ and $u \in [m_1, m_2]$ be any point. Then $\exists a \in [0, 1]$ s.t. $u = am_1 + (1 - a)m_2$, and we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(u) &= Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \\ &\leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &\leq e^{as} Q(m_1) + e^{(1-a)s} Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &< eQ(m_1) + eQ(m_2) + aE \\ &< 2eF + aE = H. \end{aligned}$$

Now, for each $u \in [m_1, m_2]$, $\exists a \in [0, \frac{m_2 - m_1}{2}]$ s.t. $u = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} + a$ or $u = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a$. We assume that $u = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} + a$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2}\right) &= Q\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} + a + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a\right) \\ &\leq (e^{\sqrt{2}a} - 1)^s Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} + a\right) + (e^{-\sqrt{2}a} - 1)^s Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a\right) \\ &\quad + aG\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} + a, \frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a, s\right) \\ &\leq (e^{\sqrt{2}a} - 1)^s Q(u) + (e^{-\sqrt{2}a} - 1)^s Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a\right) + aE \end{aligned}$$

By the use of H as the upper bound, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(u) &\geq \frac{\sqrt{2}a}{e - 1)^s} Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a\right) - Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a\right) - \sqrt{\frac{a}{e - 1)^s}} E \\ &\geq \frac{\sqrt{2}a}{e - 1)^s} Q\left(\frac{m_1 + m_2}{2} - a\right) - H - \sqrt{\frac{a}{e - 1)^s}} E = M \end{aligned}$$

□

In this section, Q is considered to be a differentiable function and $s, a \in (0, 1]$.

Theorem 3.11. Let $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a non-negative differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G . Then

$$(i) \nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) < \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} Q(m_1) + \frac{e^{(1-a)s}}{a} Q(m_2) + G(m_1, m_2, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a},$$

$$(ii) \nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) < \frac{(e^s - 1)^s(Q(m_1) - Q(m_2)) + 3Q(m_2)}{a} - \frac{o(a)}{a} + G(m_1, m_2, s)$$

Proof. (i) Using Taylor expansion and GS-exponential kind of convexity, we get

$$\begin{aligned} Q(am_1 + (1-a)m_2) &= Q(m_2 + a(m_1 - m_2)) \\ &= Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$Q(am_1 + (1-a)m_2) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \quad (3.3)$$

holds for each $m_1, m_2 \in V, a \in (0, 1]$ and for any fixed $s \in (0, 1]$.

Combining the equation (3.2), inequality (3.3) and using $(e^{1-a} - 1)^s < [(e^{1-a})^s + 1]$ for all $a \in (0, 1]$ and $s \in (0, 1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) &\leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) \\ &\quad + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \quad (3.4) \\ &< (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + [(e^{1-a})^s + 1]Q(m_2) \\ &\quad + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \end{aligned}$$

$$\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) < \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} Q(m_1) + \frac{e^{(1-a)s}}{a} Q(m_2) + G(m_1, m_2, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a}.$$

(ii) Now, we comes on the second part, from inequality (3.4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) &\leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) \\ &\quad + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &= (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) \\ &\quad - (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_2) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) \\ &\quad + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \\ &= (e^a - 1)^s [Q(m_1) - Q(m_2)] + \\ &\quad [(e^{1-a} - 1)^s + (e^a - 1)^s] Q(m_2) \\ &\quad + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \end{aligned}$$

It is clear that $(e^{1-a} - 1)^s < 2$, and $(e^a - 1)^s < 2$. Therefore, we can write

$$Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) < (e^a - 1)^s[Q(m_1) - Q(m_2)] + 4Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s).$$

This implies that

$$\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) < \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a}[Q(m_1) - Q(m_2)] + \frac{3}{a}Q(m_2) + G(m_1, m_2, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a}.$$

□

Theorem 3.12. Let $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a non-positive differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G . Then

$$\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) \leq \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a}[Q(m_1) - Q(m_2)] + G(m_1, m_2, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a}.$$

Proof. Using Taylor expansion and GS-exponential kind of convexity, we get

$$\begin{aligned} Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) &= Q(m_2 + a(m_1 - m_2)) \\ &= Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

and

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s) \quad (3.6)$$

holds for each $m_1, m_2 \in V$, $a \in [0, 1]$ and for any fixed $s \in (0, 1]$.

Combining the equation (3.5) and inequality (3.6), we have

$$Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s).$$

It can be seen easily, for all $s, a \in (0, 1]$, $(e^{1-a} - 1)^s + (e^a - 1)^s \geq 1$. Moreover, Q is a non-positive function, then the above inequality can be simplified to

$$Q(m_2) + a\nabla Q(m_2)^T(m_1 - m_2) + o(a) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + [1 - (e^a - 1)^s] Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s).$$

\Rightarrow

$$a \nabla Q(m_2)^T (m_1 - m_2) + o(a) \leq (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) - (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s)$$

Or

$$\nabla Q(m_2)^T (m_1 - m_2) \leq \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} [Q(m_1) - Q(m_2)] + G(m_1, m_2, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a}.$$

□

Corollary 3.12.1. Assume that $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a positive differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function, then

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla [Q(m_2) - Q(m_1)]^T (m_1 - m_2) < & \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} [Q(m_1) + Q(m_2)] + \frac{e^{(1-a)s}}{a} [Q(m_1) + Q(m_2)] \\ & + G(m_1, m_2, s) + G(m_2, m_1, s) - 2 \frac{o(a)}{a}. \end{aligned}$$

In case if Q is a negative valued, then

$$\nabla [Q(m_2) - Q(m_1)]^T (m_1 - m_2) \leq G(m_1, m_2, s) + G(m_2, m_1, s) - 2 \frac{o(a)}{a}.$$

Proof. As Q is a positive differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function, then by Theorem 3.11 (i), we have

$$\nabla Q(m_2)^T (m_1 - m_2) < \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} Q(m_1) + \frac{e^{(1-a)s}}{a} Q(m_2) + G(m_1, m_2, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a}. \quad (3.7)$$

Interchanging in the above inequality m_1 by m_2 , we have

$$\nabla Q(m_1)^T (m_2 - m_1) < \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} Q(m_2) + \frac{e^{(1-a)s}}{a} Q(m_1) + G(m_2, m_1, s) - \frac{o(a)}{a}. \quad (3.8)$$

Adding the inequalities in (3.7) and (3.8), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla [Q(m_2) - Q(m_1)]^T (m_1 - m_2) < & \frac{(e^a - 1)^s}{a} [Q(m_1) + Q(m_2)] + \frac{e^{(1-a)s}}{a} [Q(m_1) + Q(m_2)] \\ & + G(m_1, m_2, s) + G(m_2, m_1, s) - 2 \frac{o(a)}{a}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, if Q is a negative differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function, then by Theorem 3.12, we have

$$\nabla [Q(m_2) - Q(m_1)]^T (m_1 - m_2) \leq G(m_1, m_2, s) + G(m_2, m_1, s) - 2 \frac{o(a)}{a}.$$

□

The following methods are then utilized to apply the above outcomes to nonlinear programming. So, we take the unconstrained problem (S).

$$(S) : \min\{Q(m), m \in V\} \quad (3.9)$$

Theorem 3.13. Let $Q : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G . Also, suppose that $m \in V$ and the inequality

$$\nabla Q(m)^T (n - m) > G(n, m, s) + \frac{3Q(m) - o(a)}{a} \quad (3.10)$$

holds for each $n \in V$, $a \in (0, 1)$, and for any particular $s \in (0, 1]$, then m is the solution optimal to the problem (3.9) related to Q on V .

Proof. Let $n \in V$ be an arbitrary point, from Theorem 3.11, as Q is a positive differentiable GS-exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G , we have

$$\nabla Q(m)^T (n - m) < \frac{(e^s - 1)^s (Q(n) - Q(m)) + 3Q(m) - o(a)}{a} + G(n, m, s), \quad (3.11)$$

holds for $a \in (0, 1)$, for any number $s \in (0, 1]$, and from the given condition in this Theorem as

$$\nabla Q(m)^T (n - m) > G(n, m, s) + \frac{3Q(m) - o(a)}{a}. \quad (3.12)$$

From the inequalities (3.11) and (3.12), we have $Q(n) - Q(m) > 0$. Hence, m is the optimal solution of Q on V . \square

Example 3.14. Let's say $Q : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function defined as $Q(m) = (m^4 + 2m)^s$, for any fixed $s \in (0, 1)$ and $G : [0, \infty) \times [0, \infty) \times (0, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be defined as $G(m, n, s) = 11 + m^2 + n^2 + s^2$. Then Q is a GS-exponential kind of convex function.

Indeed, $H(m) = m^4 + 2m$ is a convex function, non-negative valued, defined on $[0, \infty)$. Combining the Corollary 7 in [1], then $H(m)$ can be shown as an s -convex function on $[0, \infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$. Also, we have

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) \leq a^s Q(m_1) + (1 - a)^s Q(m_2).$$

As $e^a - 1 \geq a \Rightarrow (e^a - 1)^s \geq a^s$, so we have

$$Q(am_1 + (1 - a)m_2) < (e^a - 1)^s Q(m_1) + (e^{1-a} - 1)^s Q(m_2) + aG(m_1, m_2, s).$$

Therefore, Q is a GS-exponential kind of convex function.

The following example of unconstrained programming is taken into consideration

$$S : \min\{Q(m), m \in [1, \infty)\} \quad (3.13)$$

where $G(m, n, s) = 11 + m^2 + n^2 + s^2$ and $Q(m) = (m^4 + 2m)^s$, here for any fixed $s \in (0, 1)$. As Q is a positive differentiable GS -exponential kind of convex function associated with the map G and for fixed $m, n \in [0, \infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. On calculation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla Q(m)^T (n - m) &= s(m^4 + 2m)^{s-1}(4m^3 + 2)(n - m), \\ \frac{3Q(m) - o(a)}{a} &= \frac{3(m^4 + 2m)^s - o(a)}{a}, \\ G(m, n, s) &= 11 + m^2 + n^2 + s^2 \end{aligned}$$

Now, at $m = 0$, the inequality $\nabla Q(m)^T (n - m) > G(n, m, s) + \frac{3Q(m) - o(a)}{a}$ holds for all $n \in [0, \infty)$, $a \in (0, 1)$ and for any particular $s \in (0, 1)$. Hence, from Theorem 3.13, the minimum value of $Q(n)$ lies at zero.

Conclusions In this present paper, we developed the idea of GS -exponential kind of convex function and established some of its algebraic features. Also, we established certain fundamental properties of GS -exponential kind of convex functions. At the end, we developed the sufficient conditions of optimality and offered unconstrained as well as inequality-constrained programming while considering the assumption of GS -exponential kind of convexity.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- [1] Alomari M, Darus M, Dragomir SS. New inequalities of Simpson's type for s -convex functions with applications. Research report collection. 2009; 12(4) .
- [2] Butt SI, Kashuri A, Nasir, J. Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities via new exponential type convexity and their applications. Filomat. 2021; 35(6), pp.1803-1822.
- [3] Du T, Wang H, Khan MA, Zhang Y. Certain integral inequalities considering generalized m -convexity on fractal sets and their applications. Fractals. 2019; 27(07), p.1950117.

- [4] Emam T. Roughly B-invex programming problems. *Calcolo*. 2011; 48(2), pp.173-188 .
- [5] Fakhari M, Mahyarinia MR Zafarani J. On nonsmooth robust multiobjective optimization under generalized convexity with applications to portfolio optimization. *European Journal of Operational Research*. 2018; 265(1), pp.39-48.
- [6] Fulga C, Preda V. Nonlinear programming with E-preinvex and local E-preinvex functions. *European Journal of Operational Research*. 2009; 192(3), pp.737-743.
- [7] Hudzik H, Maligranda L. Some remarks on s-convex functions. *Aequationes mathematicae*. 1994; 48(1), pp.100-111.
- [8] Iqbal A, Hussain A. Nonlinear programming problem for strongly E-invex sets and strongly E-preinvex functions. *RAIRO-Operations Research*. 2022; 56(3), pp.1397-1410.
- [9] Kadakal M, İşcan İ. Exponential type convexity and some related inequalities. *Journal of Inequalities and Applications*. 2020(1), pp.1-9.
- [10] Kadakal H. New Inequalities for Strongly-Convex Functions. *Journal of Function Spaces*. 2019.
- [11] Liao J, Du T. On Some Characterizations of Sub-b-s-Convex Functions. *Filomat*. 2016; 30(14), pp.3885-3895.
- [12] Long XJ, Peng JW. Semi-B-preinvex functions. *Journal of optimization theory and applications*. 2006; 131(2), pp.301-305.
- [13] Chao MT, Jian JB, Liang DY. Sub-b-convex functions and sub-b-convex programming, *Operations Research Transactions(China)*. 2012; 16, pp.1–8.
- [14] Mishra SK, Mohapatra RN, Youness EA. Some properties of semi E–b–vex functions. *Applied mathematics and Computation*. 2011; 217(12), pp.5525-5530.
- [15] Özcan S, İşcan İ. Some new Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities for s-convex functions and their applications. *Journal of inequalities and applications*. 2019(1), pp.1-11.
- [16] Shi F, Ye G, Liu W, Zhao D. cr-h-convexity and some inequalities for cr-h-convex function. *Filomat*. 2022.
- [17] Syau YR, Jia L, Lee ES. Generalizations of E-convex and B-vex functions. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications*. 2009; 58(4), pp.711-716.
- [18] Wang G, He Y. Generalized convexity of the inverse hyperbolic cosine function. *Miskolc Mathematical Notes*. 2018; 19(2), pp.873-881.
- [19] Yang XM On. E-convex sets, E-convex functions, and E-convex programming. *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications*. 2001; 109(3), p.699.

- [20] Youness E.A. E-convex sets, E-convex functions, and E-convex programming. Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications. 1999; 102(2), pp.439-450.
- [21] Zhao YX, Wang SY, Coladas Uria. L Characterizations of r-convex functions. Journal of optimization theory and applications. 2010; 145(1), pp.186-195.